

Original Research

Developing an Ethical Scale to Measure Instagram Use Motivation Among College Students: Investigating Demographic Factors

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Abstract

This study aimed to measure Instagram use motivations and explore potential differences based on gender, age, marital status, and academic background among Iranian college students. A scale was developed with 6 dimensions and 27 items, and its reliability and validity were confirmed. Statistical methods including t-tests, one-way analysis, and Friedman test were used to analyze the data. Results showed high reliability and significant differences in motivation levels and dimensions across demographic groups. Females exhibited higher motivation levels than males, and individuals above 30 years showed higher motivation. Married individuals demonstrated higher motivation levels than singles. The most prevalent motivation for using Instagram was passing time, while self-expression was the least common motivation. The scale was deemed suitable for measuring motivation levels for using Instagram among Iranian college students. The study's findings highlighted distinct patterns of motivation based on gender, age, marital status, and academic background, providing valuable insights into Instagram use. By identifying and analyzing significant motivational differences across diverse demographic factors, this study not only enriches the understanding of social media usage in a unique cultural setting but also provides a foundation for future research on social media behavior in similar contexts.

Keywords: Instagram, Motivation, Pass time, Social interaction, Social networking apps.

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Introduction

Nowadays, online social networks have penetrated in routine life and are used by billion users to share information and interact with together. Over the past years, social networks sites have become popular platforms for communication and share information (Islam, Mäntymäki, Baur, & Bick, 2018). Since smartphones are pervasive, users use their smartphones to access their social networks profile. As well as, some social networks apps were designed for smartphone's operating system like iOS and Android. Instagram was the one of these social network apps which was designed to iOS and Android operating system and at first, it was accessible only on mobile operating system (Lee E, Lee J-A, Moon J-H, & Sung Y, 2015). In recent years, Instagram website was launched and users can access their Instagram account via Instagram website too. During the last years, the number of Instagram users has increased and it has become more popular among online social networks users.

Online social networks are popular online communication platforms for users. People use online social networks to connect and reconnect with their friend and family members (Su et al., 2018; Subrahmanyam et al., 2008). Lim and Kumar (2019) suggested that people use social media because of social interaction, expression of their opinion and knowing about others. The results of a research showed that self-expression and social interaction needs are the strongest predictors of the use of Instagram among young adults in Kuwait (Al-Kandari et al., 2016). Also, these two motives are the predictor for Facebook users among Iranian users. Knowing about others is another factor that impact on online social networks (Sheldon & Bryant, 2016). People also use social media for entertainments, pass time, expression their opinions and information sharing which cause to gratification for using social media (Lim, 2019). Narcissism is a personality disorder characterized by exaggerated feelings of self-importance, excessive need for admiration, and a lack of empathy. People with narcissistic often spend much time thinking about achieving power or success, or on their appearance. This personality disorder positively related to the intention to post selfies on Instagram social network (Kim et al., 2016). Excessive use of online social networks leads to a kind of addiction to technology, which is a non-drug and behavioral addiction that leads to lack of concentration, anxiety, depression and reduced academic performance among students (Esmaeili Rad, & Ahmadi, 2017). Sheldon & Bryant (2016) showed that life satisfaction and narcissism have positive relationship with motives for Instagram use. Esmaeili Rad & Ahmadi (2019) showed that the longer you use social networks, the more you become addicted to social networks and the lower life satisfaction. Lim (2019) stated that People's gender and occupation are very influential in using Instagram because women are more inclined to share their personal interests with others, but men are more introverted. The evaluation results Hamidi (2015) showed that women are more sensitive to privacy than men and disclose their personal information less than men.

In the last few years, the appearance of online social networks and increase the use of these social networks has forced the researchers to conduct studies in this area to analyze the motives of online social networks using. Table 1 shows the main studies conducted in this area in some countries.

Table 1. The main studies in the motives for online social networking use field

Research	Subject of Study	Results
(Sheldon & Bryant, 2016)	To investigate motives for Instagram use and its relationship to contextual age and narcissism.	There is a positive relationship between interpersonal interaction and using Instagram for coolness, creative purpose and surveillance. Also, there is positive relationship between social activity and motive for Instagram use and there is a positive relationship between using Instagram to be cool and for surveillance.
(M. Dumas et al., 2017)	To examine Instagram like-seeking behavior and motives for Instagram use.	Normative like-seeking is predicted by stronger narcissism and a stronger sense of peer belonging and there is a mediator of relation between narcissism and deceptive like-seeking included motives to use Instagram to increase popularity and showcase creativity.
(Oliveira & Huertas, 2015)	To investigate the influence of life satisfaction on motive for Facebook use.	The life satisfaction has influence on motive for Facebook use.
(W. Davenport et al., 2014)	Exploring the role of narcissism in the motives and usage of different social media platforms.	Narcissism is a stronger predictor of Twitter active usage than Facebook active usage in both the college and adult sample.
(Lup et al., 2015)	Exploring the association between Instagram use and depressive symptoms through the mechanism of negative social comparison, and moderation by number of strangers one follows.	Instagram use is positively associated with depressive symptoms and mount of strangers followed moderated the associations of Instagram use with social comparison and depressive symptoms.
(Nedraa et al., 2019)	In order to examine the factors that impact on intention to use Instagram.	Perceived pleasure, social identity (cognitive, affective and evaluative) and perceived ease of use have positive effect on intention to use Instagram.
(Kim & Kim, 2018)	In order to explore which factors are associated with the usage level of Facebook and Instagram.	Users who were more gratified with the entertainment and need for recognition aspects of gratifications increasingly use Facebook and those users that have positive attitudes toward Facebook's recommendation algorithm features use Facebook more and users who are gratified with the

Research	Subject of Study	Results
		browsing aspect of gratifications increasingly used Instagram and who have positive attitudes toward levels of openness on Instagram increasingly use Instagram.
(Kim et al., 2016)	To investigate the antecedents of selfie-posting behavior on Social Networks Sites	Attitude toward selfie-posting, subjective norm, perceived behavioral control, and narcissism are significant predictors to an individual's intention to post selfies on Social Networking Sites.
(Al-Kandari et al., 2016)	In order to examine the need and motives of Instagram users that predict self-disclosure use.	Self-expression and social interaction needs are the strongest predictors of the use of Instagram.
(Ting et al., 2015)	In order to serve as groundwork to explore Why people use Instagram in Malaysia.	Behavioral beliefs about Instagram are five factors: personal gratification, features usefulness, socializing role, product information and entertainment and normative beliefs are six factors: siblings, relatives, close friends/peers, friends in general, Facebook friends, and application reviewers.
(Krishen et al. 2019)	Social media networking satisfaction in the US and Vietnam: Content versus connection.	It uses fuzzy set qualitative comparative analysis to find that both cultures value belonging, affinity, and interactivity. In terms of differences, Vietnamese derive higher satisfaction from system quality and emotional connection, and Americans indicate higher satisfaction from information quality.
(Borges and thiago, 2019)	Exploring users' motivations to participate in viral communication on social media	It is an essential and important channel for user to online advertising, communication with other, and engagement.
(Su et al., 2018)	To examine the profiles, gender, digital opportunities, and patterns of motives for using social networking sites	The primary motive of using social networks sites was connecting with others. Also, there was a significant difference between connecting, sharing, organizing, and monitoring in gender groups, and in connecting, sharing, relaxing, branding, monitoring, and expressing between pupils with different digital

Research	Subject of Study	Results
		opportunities due to regional digital development.
(Pittman & Reich, 2016)	To test the effect of image-based and text-based social media use on loneliness, happiness and life satisfaction.	Image-based social media use such as Instagram decreases loneliness and increases happiness and satisfaction with life.
(Lee et al., 2015)	In order to determine the motives for using Instagram.	Users have the following motives for using Instagram: social interaction, archiving, self-expression, escapism, and peeking.
(Subrahmanyam et al., 2008)	In order to determine what college students did online, how much time they spent on various online activities, especially on social networking sites and instant messaging.	users use social networks sites to connect with their friends and family members.
(Kirkaburn et al. 2019)	Analyzing the Links Between Social Media Use, and Self-esteem	One of the motivations for using social media is to be fun and entertaining.
(Saeidnia & Ghorbanzadeh, 2016)	In order to investigate the factors influencing the attitudes of Telegram users and its impact on positive word of mouth from the view point of the Iranian students.	The technical characteristics of telegram, perceived usefulness, and trust have a positive impact on the attitude of Telegram users.

Research on user motivations for new media in our country has been limited, with insufficient focus on the communicative needs of internet users engaging with social media. As media organizations aim to establish a presence in this environment, understanding the motivating factors influencing users' attraction to social networks becomes crucial. Existing studies primarily address user motivations for social media use, lacking an examination of the differences in motivations for using Instagram across various demographic groups. This study aims to analyze the variations in motivation to use Instagram based on gender, age, marital status, and education level among Iranian students, as well as to explore the distinctions in motivational dimensions across these categories.

Material & Methods

In this research, a scale was designed to measure the level of motivation for using Instagram. Based on previous studies 27 items was gathered to measure the motivation for using Instagram. These items consist 6 dimensions: pass time, self-assertion, Interest

to increase followers, knowing about others, self-expression and social interaction. Definition of each item is provided below. Meanwhile the conceptual model of motivation for using Instagram is showed in figure1.

Pass time: refers to using Instagram to occupy time, spent more time on Instagram and prefer using of Instagram to spend time with their family as well as doing personal activities and sleep.

self-assertion: refers to users who think that they are better than others, special and unique. And they think that their posts are attractive for all users. They often care about that who likes their posts and don't pay attention other users' posts.

Interest to increase followers: refers to interest to increase the number of followers. Users who post photos or videos and change their profile picture frequently desire to increase their Instagram followers.

Knowing about others: refers to see what other people share, like their friends' photos and see visual status updates of their friends (Sheldon P & Bryant K, 2016).

Self-expression: refers to share their opinion about important events and share a post about daily issues.

social interaction: refers to find new people and interact with them, like all post of other people and spend more time on Instagram to interact with people.

Participants were 385 college students who use Instagram. This number has been obtained using Cochran's formula for an infinite population. These participants were randomly selected among Iranian college students and the Cochran formula was used to calculate the sample size. Table 1 shows the demographic information of participants. In order to develop the scale, the items of scale were obtained from pervious researches. 27 items were gathered that each item score ranging 1 to 5 (1=never to 5=always). The scale consists 6 dimensions measuring the levels of Instagram motives use. In order to ensure that construct was properly reflected in this scale and to validate it in the Persian language, some language and psychology experts investigated the scale. Then, the scale was sent to participants and data were collected. After removing noise, data were analyzed to evaluate the reliability and validity.

Figure 1. The conceptual model of motivation for using Instagram

Analysis of the collected data was performed using the SPSS package program. Besides descriptive analyses, the reliability of the scale was assessed by calculating the Cronbach's alpha coefficient and the confirmatory factor analysis was used to verify the validity of the scale. To analysis of research hypotheses, independent t-test, one-way analysis and non-parametric Friedman test were done by IBM SPSS Statistics 23.

The 0.837 overall internal consistency was calculated for the scale that can be considered as an indicator of high reliability. The proposed scale has 6 dimensions: pass time, self-assertion, Interest to increase followers, knowing about others, self-expression and social interaction. table 2 shows the Values of Cronbach's alpha for these dimensions. These results indicated that the reliability of all dimensions of scale is acceptable.

Table 1. Demographic Profile of Participants

Variable	Scale	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Female	185	48.1
	Male	200	51.9
Age	Less Than 20	39	10.1
	Between 20 To 25	188	48.9
	Between 26 To 30	111	28.1
	More Than 30	47	12.2
Academic degree	Associate	48	12.5
	Bachelor	230	59.7
	Master	101	26.2
	PhD	6	1.6
Marital status	Single	214	55.6
	Married	171	44.4
Total		385	100

Table 2. Scale internal consistency

Dimensions	Number of items	Alpha
Pass time	10	0.902
self-assertion	3	0.752
Interest to increase followers	4	0.701
knowing about others	4	0.765
Self-expression	2	0.770
social interaction	4	0.710
motivation for using Instagram	27	0.837

Scale constructs validity: Confirmatory factor analysis

In order to verify the construct validity of the scale, the confirmatory factor analysis was conducted. Before carrying out analysis, the sampling adequacy was verified. The value of $KMO=0.816 > 0.8$ showed a high correlation between data, therefore, the sampling was adequate. In addition, the value of $p=0.000$ indicated that the confirmatory factor analysis can be considered as an appropriate technique. Table 3 shows the results of factor loading of motivation for using Instagram scale. The results of factor loading for all questions are more than 0.4. The obtained indices were $RMSEA=0.001$, $GFI=0.90$, $NFI=0.92$, $NNFI=0.92$, $IFI=0.93$, $CFI=0.92$, these results indicated a good fit of data to the model. Also, the relationship $\chi^2/\text{degree of freedom}$ has a value of 0.195 which is acceptable.

Table 3. factor loading of motivation for using Instagram scale items

Dimension	Items	Factor loading
self-expression	Q1	0.516
	Q2	0.420
knowing about others	Q3	0.796
	Q4	0.714

Dimension	Items	Factor loading
	Q5	0.629
	Q6	0.579
social interaction	Q7	0.413
	Q8	0.496
	Q9	0.963
	Q10	0.865
Interest to increase followers	Q11	0.876
	Q12	0.823
	Q13	0.831
	Q14	0.759
Pass time	Q15	0.789
	Q16	0.780
	Q17	0.741
	Q18	0.602
	Q19	0.403
	Q20	0.415
	Q21	0.582
	Q22	0.555
	Q23	0.496
self-assertion	Q24	0.523
	Q25	0.581
	Q26	0.511
	Q27	0.433

In order to determine whether the data follows a normal distribution, Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used. Table 4 shows the results.

Table 4. Results of Normality test

Variable	Test statistic	Sig. (2-tailed)	distribution
age	0.98	0.098	normal
gender	1.02	0.055	normal
academic degree	0.49	0.062	normal
marital status	0.22	0.115	normal
Motivation for using Instagram	0.45	0.406	normal
self-expression	0.186	0.000	non-normal
knowing about others	0.098	0.000	non-normal
social interaction	0.143	0.000	non-normal
interest to increase followers	0.105	0.000	non-normal
pass time	0.098	0.000	non-normal
self-assertion	0.169	0.000	non-normal

Results

Independent t-test was performed to assess the difference between the mean score of motivation for using Instagram in different gender groups Table 5 indicated that there was significantly difference between male and female in the level of motivation using from Instagram and mean of motivation for using Instagram for female group (M=96.38, SD=12.46) was significantly higher than male group (M=93.48, SD=13.23), $t(383) = 2.192$, $P = .029 < .05$. Thus, H2 was accepted.

Table 5. T test result for gender

variable	number	mean	Std. Deviation	Mean difference	t	df	Sig.
female	225	96.386	12.466	2.899	2.192	383	.029
male	160	93.487	13.230				
single	185	93.708	10.689	-2.84	-2.1999	365.551	.028
married	200	96.545	14.464				

Non-parametric Friedman test of difference among dimensions of motivation for using Instagram in male group was conducted and rendered a Chi-square value of 853.04 which was significant ($P = .000 < .05$) (see Table 6). And in this group, the mean rank of pass time was more and self- expression was less than other variables (see Table 7). Also, results indicated that there was a significant difference among dimensions of motivation for using Instagram in female group (Chi-square=590.509, $P = .000 < .05$). About female group the mean rank of pass time was more than other variables and the mean rank of self-expression was less than others too (see Table 7). Therefore, H6 and H7 were accepted.

Table 6. Test Statistics of Friedman

variable	Number	Chi-square	df	Asymp. Sig.
male	225	853.034	5	.000
female	160	590.509	5	.000
less than 20	49	188.946	5	.000
between 20 to 25	192	732.278	5	.000
between 26 to 30	102	366.437	5	.000
more than 30	42	161.209	5	.000
single	185	692.995	5	.000
married	200	749.316	5	.000
associate	43	159.121	5	.000
bachelor	241	907.810	5	.000
master	95	350.609	5	.000
PhD	6	26.163	5	.000

Table 7. Friedman test Results

variable		self-expression	knowing about others	social interaction	interest to increase followers	pass time	self-assertion
Mean rank of gender	male	1.22	4.06	3.52	3.78	6.00	2.43
	female	1.18	3.90	3.49	3.81	5.99	2.63
Mean rank of age	less than 20	1.07	4.01	3.60	3.63	6.00	2.68
	between 20 to 25	1.20	3.98	3.54	3.86	6.00	2.43
	between 26 to 30	1.21	3.88	3.44	3.74	5.99	2.75
	more than 30	1.38	4.27	3.42	3.79	6.00	2.14
Mean rank of married status	single	1.20	3.95	3.57	3.80	6.00	2.49
	married	1.21	4.03	3.45	3.79	6.00	2.54
Mean rank of academic degree	associate	1.16	3.97	3.55	3.72	5.98	2.63
	bachelor	1.22	4.05	3.48	3.78	6.00	2.47
	master	1.19	3.86	3.54	3.82	6.00	2.59
	PhD	1.00	3.83	3.75	4.17	6.00	2.25

Motivation for using Instagram and age

The one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine whether there was any statistically significant difference between the means of motivation for using Instagram in four “less than 20 years”, “between 20 to 25 years”, “between 26 to 30 years” and “more than 30 years” groups. Results showed that there was a significant difference between groups ($F(3, 381) = 9.07, p = .001 < 0.05$) (see Table 8). According to result of Leven test ($p = .00 < 0.05$) (see Table 8) Post hoc comparisons using the Games-Howell test was conducted and results of the Games-Howell test (see Table 9) indicated that there was a significant difference between “more than 30 years” group and “less than 20 years” ($MD = 10.32, p = .001 < 0.05$). As well as there was a significant difference between “more than 30 years” and “between 20 to 25 years” groups ($MD = 5.88, p = .000 < 0.05$), and there was a significant difference between “more than 30” group and “between 26 to 30 years” ($MD = 10.69, p = .000 < 0.05$). According to results, the mean of motivation for using Instagram in “more than 30” group was more than other groups. Also, there was a significant difference between “between 20 to 25 years” group and “between 26 to 30 years” group ($MD = 4.81, p = .012 < 0.05$) and the mean of motivation for using Instagram in “between 20 to 25 years” was more than “between 26 to 30 years” group. Thus, H_3 was accepted.

Table 8. Results of ANOVA tests for age

variable		df	F	Sig.	Test of Homogeneity of variance	
age	Between group	3	9.07	.001	Leven statistic	
	Within group	381			12.266	.000
	Total	384				
gender	Between group	3	1.62	.184		
	Within group	381				
	Total	384				

Table 9. Results of Games-Howell test for age

variable		Mean difference	Sig.
less than 20	between 20 to 25	-4.44	.298
	between 26 to 30	.37	.999
	more than 30	-10.32*	.001
between 20 to 25	less than 20	4.44	.298
	between 26 to 30	4.81*	.012
	more than 30	-5.88*	.000
between 26 to 30	less than 20	-.37	.999
	between 20 to 25	-4.81*	.012
	more than 30	-10.69*	.000
more than 30	less than 20	10.32*	.001
	between 20 to 25	5.88*	.000
	between 26 to 30	10.69*	.000

Non-parametric Friedman test of difference among dimensions of motivation for using Instagram in different age group was conducted. The results of this test indicated in Table 6 and 7. The results rendered that there was a significant difference among dimensions of motivation for using Instagram in “less than 20 years” group (Chi-square=188.946, $P=.000<.05$) and the mean rank of pass time was more and self-expression was less than other variables. Also, results indicated that there was a significant difference among dimensions of motivation for using Instagram in “between 20 to 25 years” group (Chi-square=732.278, $P=.000<.05$). As well as, the mean rank of pass time was more than other dimensions and self-expression was less than other dimensions. According to the results there was a significant difference among dimensions of motivation for using Instagram in “between 26 to 30 years” group too (Chi-square=366.437, $P=.000<.05$) and the mean rank of pass time was more than other variables and self-expression was less than other variables. Also, about “more than 30 years” group results showed that there was a significant difference among dimensions of motivation for using Instagram in this group (Chi-square=161.209, $P=.000<.05$) and like other groups the mean rank of pass time was more than other dimensions and self-expression was less than other dimensions. Thus, H8, H9, H10 and H11 were accepted.

Motivation for using Instagram and married status

Independent t-test was performed to assess the difference between the mean score of motivation for using Instagram in different married status group (table 5). Results indicated that there was significantly difference between motivation using from Instagram in single and married groups and motivation score for married group ($M=96.54$, $SD=14.46$) was significantly higher than single group ($M=93.70$, $SD=10.68$), $t(365.551)=-2.199$, $P=.028<.05$. Therefore, H4 was accepted.

Non-parametric Friedman test of difference among dimensions of motivation for using Instagram in both single and married groups was conducted. (table 6 and 7). The results in single group rendered a Chi-square value of 692.995 which was significant ($P=.000<.05$) and the mean rank of pass time was more and self-expression was less than other variables. Also, results indicated that there was a significant difference among

dimensions of motivation for using Instagram in married group (Chi-square=749.316, $P=.000<.05$). According to results in married group the mean rank of pass time was more and self-expression was less than other dimensions too. Thus, H12 and H13 were accepted.

Academic degree and Motivation for using Instagram

The one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine whether there was any statistically significant difference between the means of motivation for using Instagram in four associate, bachelor, master, PhD groups. Results showed that there was no statistically significant difference between groups ($p=.184>0.05$). (see Table 8). Thus, H5 was rejected.

Non-parametric Friedman test of difference among dimensions of motivation for using Instagram in different academic degree groups was performed and results of this test indicated in Table 6 and 7. Results rendered a Chi-square value of 159.121 for associate group which was significant ($P=.000<.05$) and the mean rank of pass time was more and self-expression was less than other variables. Also, results demonstrated that there was a significant difference among dimensions of motivation for using Instagram in bachelor group (Chi-square=907.810, $P=.000<.05$) and the mean rank of pass time was more and self-expression was less than other variables. According to the results, there was a significant difference among dimensions of motivation for using Instagram in between Master group (Chi-square=350.609, $P=.000<.05$) too and the mean rank of pass time was more than other dimensions and self-expression was less than other dimensions. Also, about PhD group results showed that there was a significant difference among dimensions of motivation for using Instagram in this group (Chi-square=26.163, $P=.000<.05$) and the mean rank of pass time was more than other dimensions and self-expression was less than other dimensions too. Accordingly, H14, H15, H16, H17 were accepted.

Discussion

This research was conducted to determine whether there was any difference in the level of motivation for using Instagram in different gender, age, married status and academic degree groups. Meanwhile it was performed to investigate dimensions of motivation for using. For this purpose, at first, a scale was designed for measure the level of motivation for Instagram use. the results indicated that the reliability of all dimensions and the scale are acceptable. It is notable Al-Kandari A et al., (2016) proposed a scale with 5 dimensions and the other previous scale includes 4 dimensions (Sheldon P & Bryant K, 2016). In order to evaluate the construct validity of the scale, the confirmatory factor analysis was conduct in the rest. the results indicated a good fit of data to the model. So, the designed scale has acceptable reliability and validity to measure the motivation for Instagram use.

In order to investigate the other hypotheses of the research and determine the difference of motivation for using Instagram in different groups, t-test and one-way analysis were conducted. The finding indicated that there was a significant difference in motivation for using Instagram between male and female and mean of motivation for using Instagram in female group was significantly higher than male group. The one-way

analysis results showed that there was a significant difference for motivation of using Instagram between different age groups. Results showed that the mean of motivation of using for Instagram in “more than 30 years” groups was more than other groups. About the relationship between married status and motivation for using Instagram, the results of t-test indicated that there was significantly difference between motivation using Instagram in single and married groups. Motivation score for married group was significantly higher than single group. The results of ANOVA for testing motivation in different academic degree groups showed that there was no statistically significant difference between groups.

In addition, in this research, Non-parametric Friedman test was performed to determine whether there was any significantly difference among dimensions of motivation for using Instagram. The finding suggested that there was a significant difference among dimensions of motivation for using Instagram in male group. And the mean rank of pass time was more than other variables and the mean rank of self-expression was less than others. As well as, there was a significant difference among dimensions of motivation for using Instagram in female group and the mean rank of pass time was more than other variables and the mean rank of self-expression was less than others too. About investigating different age groups results demonstrated that there was a significant difference among dimensions of motivation in various groups. About, married status the results showed the mean rank of pass time was more and self-expression was less than other variables. Also, there was a significant difference among dimensions of motivation for using Instagram in married group. in married group the mean rank of pass time was more and self-expression was less than other dimensions too. Finally, results of different academic degree groups indicated that there was a significant difference among different dimensions of motivation of using Instagram in associate group and the mean rank of pass time was more and self-expression was less than other variables. Also, there was a significant difference among dimensions of motivation for using Instagram in educational groups.

Several recent studies have concluded that men are more likely to disclose their personal address and mobile phone number, but share fewer private profiles than women and women are more interested in using social networks such as Instagram to increase their social relationships (krasnova et al., 2013). In our research we show this subject with H2 and H6 and H7 and these hypotheses accepted. Research has shown that gender also affects the use of social networks, especially Instagram (rayes et al., 2022). The gender, knowledge and interest of all of them are important to the motivations and behavior of using the Internet. University elders are also influential in thinking, and mastery of the brain affects not only thinking but also the behavior of using the Internet (Sheldon 2016). In our research we show this subject with H2, H15, H16, H17 that accepted.

People under the age of 35 welcome Instagram because of their psychological characteristics such as narcissism and attraction. Therefore, people with this age range are more interested in using Instagram. Also, for people over the age of 50, learning and working on Instagram is a challenge for them, so this is a deterrent to using Instagram at an older age. Most of the users of this site are people who are younger and want to communicate more externally (pew research center, 2022). we show this subject with H8,

H9, H10, H11 that accepted. Therefore, our research is consistent with other research in terms of indicators.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study successfully developed a reliable and valid scale to measure motivations for using Instagram among Iranian college students. The findings revealed significant differences in motivation levels and dimensions based on gender, age, marital status, and academic background. Specifically, females exhibited higher motivation levels than males, while individuals above 30 years of age showed greater motivation compared to younger age groups. Moreover, married individuals demonstrated higher motivation levels than singles. The most prevalent motivation for using Instagram was found to be passing time, while self-expression was the least common motivation. These results provide valuable insights into the diverse reasons individuals engage with the Instagram platform. The study contributes to a better understanding of social media usage patterns and can inform targeted interventions and platform design to cater to the specific motivations of different user groups.

Ethical consideration

The protection of participant privacy and data confidentiality was the primary ethical consideration of this research. It was essential to ensure that personal information and participant responses remained confidential and were not disclosed in any manner that could lead to identification. Researchers obtained informed consent from participants, clearly outlining the study's purpose, how their data would be used, and the measures in place to protect their privacy. Furthermore, the researchers adhered to ethical guidelines concerning the collection, storage, and use of personal data, particularly in sensitive contexts like social media usage among college students.

Limitations and future researches

One of the limitations of this study was statistical population of research. It covered the college students in Iran. Therefore, future studies should seek out larger and more diverse samples. Future studies can examine the impact of other factors such as narcissisms, life satisfactions, depression and anxiety on motivation for using Instagram.

Conflict of Interest

On behalf of all authors, the corresponding author states that there is no conflict of interest.

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